

OUTCOME OF STAPLES IN MESH FIXATION IN LICHTENSTEIN'S INGUINAL HERNIA REPAIR IN ABBASI SHAHEED HOSPITAL

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17695550>

Keywords

operative time, mesh fixation, staples, Lichtenstein's, inguinal hernia.

Article History

Received: 01 October 2025

Accepted: 10 November 2025

Published: 24 November 2025

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: Inguinal hernia is an important diagnosis and the kind of repair done holds importance in the surgical outcome and its impact on recovery.

OBJECTIVE To analyze the mean operative time and frequency of moderate to severe pain in patients who receive mesh fixation by staples during Lichtenstein's inguinal hernia repair.

METHODS it is a descriptive study, conducted at the department of Surgery, Abbasi Shaheed Hospital Karachi, from 10th Nov 2020 to 10th May 2021. Severity of post-op pain was observed and recorded via proforma at 24th post-op hour as injectable analgesics were switched to oral tablets, patients were fully mobilized and most of them were discharged. Included were 95 patients having elective inguinal hernia repairs. The mean age was 53.115 ± 8.199 years.

RESULTS The mean operative time was 30.926 ± 6.656 minutes. The severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs was mild in 36 patients (37.9%), moderate in 11(11.6%) & severe in 5(5.3%). Operative time in majority of the patients was half an hour. The majority of patients experienced mild to moderate postoperative pain following staple fixation of mesh in Lichtenstein's inguinal hernioplasty. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to ascertain how staples in mesh fixation affect the result of inguinal hernia repair in Lichtenstein. This study will highlight the benefits and significance of more efficient and superior technique and will serve as guide for surgeons in future. A novel approach to treating inguinal hernias has been devised, in which staples, rather than polypropylene suture, are used to secure prolene mesh.

INTRODUCTION

Inguinal hernia is a frequent surgical disease [1]. Inguinal hernia surgery is a commonly performed surgery at any healthcare centre. Its repair is one of the most frequently performed procedures with minor considerable morbidities like wound infection and recurrence. It represents from 17.2% to 24% of all surgeries [2]. It has been a great deal of discussion over the past 20 years over the usefulness of mesh prosthesis for wall reinforcement. In the end, meta-

analysis demonstrated that mesh repair reduced the frequency of recurrence [3].

For the repair of inguinal hernias, the Lichtenstein tension-free repair has taken precedence [4]. It involves using polypropylene sutures to fasten the mesh in place on the inguinal canal's posterior wall. Currently, 80-90% of inguinal hernia surgeries are performed using this straightforward and quick technique [5] [6]. Sutures may result in muscle fiber

strangling or even a lesion or compression of the local nerves, causing chronic pain or dysesthesia, despite the "tension-free" aspect of these procedures [7].

Post-operative discomfort is one of the most common consequences following abdominal wall hernia surgery. This pain can worsen one's quality of life and turn chronic and permanent [8]. An additional method of fastening the mesh is by use of stapling device [9]. The use of staples to secure the mesh during hernia repair was initially documented by Egger et al [10].

Similar research comparing staples and polypropylene sutures for fastening the mesh in inguinal hernioplasty was published by Mills et al. and Zwaal et al [6][11]. Fifty elective primary inguinal hernia repairs under general anesthesia were reported by Mills et al. According to his study, the use of skin staples to secure the mesh in the Lichtenstein inguinal hernia repair significantly shortened the operation's duration from 29 minutes and 30 seconds (24 minutes to 43 minutes and 45 seconds) in the control group (where the mesh was secured with polypropylene sutures) to about 20 minutes (16 minutes to 33 minutes and 15 seconds) in the study group. In the short term, this method was just as effective as conventional mesh fixation with polypropylene, but there was no discernible difference in pain scores [6].

Zwaal et al. analyzed 149 elective cases of primary inguinal hernia repair and concluded that out of 82 patients who had their mesh fixed with staples, 29 (51%) had no pain, 20 (35%) patients had mild pain and 8 (14%) patients had moderate to severe pain post-operatively according to visual analogue score (VAS) [11].

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to ascertain how staples in mesh fixation affect the result of inguinal hernia repair in Lichtenstein. In order for the decision to apply this approach to be made confidently. This study will highlight the benefits and significance of a more efficient and superior technique and will serve as a guide for fellow surgeons in future. With reduced duration of operative procedure, patients will be at low risk of developing anesthesia related complications. Reduction in the pain intensity will further improve the post-operative quality of life in these patients.

The objective of this study is to analyze the mean operative time and frequency of moderate to severe pain in patients who receive mesh fixation by staples during Lichtenstein's inguinal hernia repair.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It is a descriptive study, conducted at Abbasi Shaheed Hospital, Karachi, from 10th Nov 2020 to 10th May 2021. The sample size was found to be 95 cases of indirect inguinal hernias, with confidence level of 95% and margin of error 7%, including patients in age group 21-70yrs with reducible unilateral indirect inguinal hernia of not more than 3months duration, operated electively under spinal anesthesia having ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) class 1 & 2. While, excluding female gender, recurrent hernias, ASA class ≥ 3 and complicated inguinal hernias (Emergency surgeries, bowel obstruction, strangulation, perforation). After obtaining informed consent, demographic data and duration of hernia was recorded on a structured proforma. Anesthesia fitness was sought. All patients had fixation of mesh with staples in Lichtenstein's tension free repair. All surgeries included in the study was performed by 3rd and 4th year residents under supervision of consultants. Staples was placed using rotating head stapler of size 6.9 x 3.9mm. Approximately eight to ten staple pins was used. Duration of surgery was noted from the time of incision to the closure of skin. All patients received a single dose of prophylactic antibiotics and analgesia cover post-operatively (Inj. Diclofenac Sodium 75mg I/M BD on same post-op day and Tab. Ponstan Forte 1 x TDS from 1st post-op day onwards). Severity of post-op pain was observed and recorded for each patient at 24hrs. Pain scoring was done at 24th post-op hour as injectable analgesics were switched to oral tablets, patients were fully mobilized and most of them was discharged. SPSS version 21 was used for data entry and analysis. Quantitative variables such as age, height, weight, BMI, duration of hernia, operative time was described as mean with standard deviation. Qualitative data such as gender, severity of post-operative pain was described as frequencies and percentages. Effect modifiers were controlled through stratification of patient's age, gender, BMI, duration of hernia. Chi-square test was applied for post-stratification. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was

taken as statistically significant. Sampling technique used is non-probability consecutive sampling. CPSP Research Reference No :CPSP/REU/SGR-2018-174-9899 approved on date March 17,2022 by Research Evaluation unit CPSP

RESULT: A total of 95 patients with inguinal hernia who received mesh fixation by staples during Lichtenstein’s inguinal hernia repair were selected to conduct this study. The mean age was 53.115±8.199 years, the mean height was 1.567±0.241 m & the mean weight was 54.876±13.698 kg. The mean BMI was 14.989±5.995 kg/m², the mean duration of hernia was 14.989±5.995 months & the mean total duration of surgery (operative time) was

30.926±6.656 minutes. In our study severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs was mild in 36 patients (37.9%), moderate in 11(11.6%), severe in 5(5.3%) & 43 (45.3%) had no pain, as shown in Table-1. The frequencies of age groups (years), duration of hernia were calculated according to severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs. The results are presented in Table-2 & Table-3 respectively. In our study the severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs was not significantly associated with age (p=0.321), duration of hernia (p=0.868)

TABLE - 1

Frequency distribution of post-operative pain at 24hrs (n=95)
severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs was mild in 36 patients (37.9%), moderate in 11(11.6%), severe in 5(5.3%) & 43 (45.3%) had no pain

Post-operative pain at 24hrs	Frequency Percentage (%)
Mild	37.9%
Moderate	11.6%
Severe	5.3%
None	45.3%
Total	100%

TABLE - 2

Severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs according to age (years) (n=95)
Chi-square test applied(P-value<0.05 considered as significant) significant at 0.05 level
The frequencies of age groups (years), duration of hernia were calculated according to severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs.

Age (years)	Severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs				Total	P-value
	Mild	Moderate	Severe	None		
21-45 years	7(7.4%)	1(1.1%)	2(2.1%)	5(5.3%)	15(15.8%)	0.321
46-70 years	29(30.5%)	10(10.5%)	3(3.2%)	38(40%)	80(84.2%)	
Total	36(37.9%)	11(11.6%)	5(5.3%)	43(45.3%)	95(100%)	

TABLE - 3

Severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs according to duration of hernia (months) (n=95)
Chi-square test applied
P-value <0.05 considered as significant
Significant at 0.05 level

The frequencies of age groups (years), duration of hernia were calculated according to severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs.

Duration of hernia (months)	Severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs				Total	P-value
	Mild	Moderate	Severe	None		
5-15	17(17.9%)	6(6.3%)	3(3.2%)	24(25.3%)	50(52.6%)	0.868
16-26	19(20%)	5(5.3%)	2(2.1%)	19(20%)	45(47.4%)	
Total	36(37.9%)	11(11.6%)	5(5.3%)	43(45.3%)	95(100%)	

DISCUSSION:

Around 5% of male population commonly affects from inguinal hernia. [12] More than 100 years ago, the basis of existing method of inguinal herniorrhapy was described by Edward bassini. [13] However, many amendments have been made to this. [14]A prosthetic mesh was described by Lichtenstein for repair of inguinal hernia.15 Originally, a polypropylene 2/0 suture is used to secure the mesh to the posterior wall of the inguinal canal. But when evaluating medical procedures—and particularly surgical ones—quality of life is becoming a more important factor to take into account. A number of postoperative quality of life indicators, including pain and healing, have been evaluated in the context of inguinal hernia repair. [16] [17] A novel approach to treating inguinal hernias has been devised, in which staples, rather than polypropylene suture, are used to secure prolene mesh to the posterior wall of the inguinal canal. In our study severity of post-operative pain at 24hrs was mild in 36 patients (37.9%), moderate in 11(11.6%), severe in 5(5.3%) & 43 (45.3%) had no pain as compare to Zwaal et al [18] , analyzed 149 elective cases of primary inguinal hernia repair and concluded that out of 82 patients who had their mesh fixed with staples, 29 (51%) had no pain, 20 (35%) patients had mild pain and 8 (14%) patients had moderate to severe pain post-operatively according to visual analogue score (VAS). Prior research indicated that staples were preferable than sutures for attaching mesh in Lichtenstein repairs. Because of its covering and shorter surgical length, staples are regarded as inert. Applying staples takes a lot less time than using polypropylene suture. Hence leading to reduce operative time. [19] [20]. The

technique of Lichtenstein repair for inguinal hernia is considered to be effective and recurrence rate is also low. Recently, a systematic review of randomized clinical trials (RCTs) has been published considering only chronic groin pain and hernia recurrence rate [26].Surgeons employ it effectively and with positive outcomes. The benefit of a shorter operating time was highlighted by Egger et al., the first author to explain the staple adjustment to this procedure. Mills et al.[21] [22]examined fifty individuals who had surgery using staples or sutures. The primary benefit of using staples in Lichtenstein repair is a reduction in operating time. A noteworthy 12-minute difference was seen between groups I and II in the Munghate et al.[23] [24] [25]investigation. As application of staples is quicker than sutures, it saves time and reduce risk of infection and complications of prolonged anesthesia.[26] Patient-reported chronic pain 1 year after open mesh repair of inguinal hernia was common, particularly in young men. The risk of developing chronic pain was not influenced by the type of mesh(27) Similar results were also shown by Garg et al.[24] Lichtenstein tension-free repair is a straightforward, less technically complex, and easier technique to master. When it comes to mesh fixation, staples may be put considerably more quickly than sutures, which reduces operating time. The location of the stapler allows for strong mesh fixation and adequate tissue penetration. There is no correlation between the usage of staples and increased postoperative pain. Using staples is an economical choice. Further research with larger sample sizes is necessary because the single center study and smaller sample size were the study's limitations.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion operative time in majority of the patients was half an hour. The postoperative pain after fixation of mesh with staples, in Lichtenstein's inguinal hernioplasty, was mild in severity followed by moderate. The severity of postoperative pain increases with the increase in age.

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